

FUEL SUBSIDY REMOVAL AND RURAL HOUSEHOLDS IN NIGERIA: A STUDY OF IKOT EKPENE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

The removal of fuel subsidies in Nigeria has sparked extensive debate, particularly regarding its effects on vulnerable rural populations. This study investigates the impact of fuel subsidy removal on rural households in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The research aimed to examine how the policy affects household food access, income generation, and healthcare access in the region. Theoretical insights were drawn from the Dependency Theory, which highlights how rural communities in developing countries often depend on centralized policies. The study employed a quantitative research approach, using structured questionnaires administered to respondents in either English or Annang language, ensuring accurate data collection. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The findings revealed significant negative effects of the subsidy removal on household food access, with most respondents reporting higher food prices and reduced availability. Additionally, income generation opportunities were severely impacted, as increased operational costs in agriculture led to a decline in earnings. Furthermore, access to healthcare worsened, with higher transportation costs and reduced disposable income making healthcare less accessible for rural households. In light of these findings, the study recommends several measures to alleviate the negative impacts which include the implementation of targeted compensation programs for vulnerable households, promoting alternative energy solutions like solar power, providing subsidies to support the agricultural sector, and improving healthcare infrastructure in rural areas.

KEYWORDS: Fuel Subsidy Removal, Rural Households, Food Access, Income Generation, and Healthcare Access.

INTRODUCTION

The removal of fuel subsidies is a topic of global debate, especially concerning its effects on vulnerable populations. While subsidies aim to make energy more affordable, they lead to market distortions and significant fiscal burdens on governments. In 2022, global fossil fuel subsidies were estimated at \$1 trillion, prompting discussions on reforming these subsidies to promote sustainable development (Ozili 2023). Nigeria is one of the largest oil producers in the world. The country is highly endowed with immeasurable mineral resources, most notably gas reserves and crude oil. Siddig and Walmsley (2019) argued that Nigeria owns 28% of Africa's oil reserve beaten by only Libya. The country produced 2.5 million barrels per day in 2017 which accounted for around 24% of Africa's petroleum (Onwuenyi, 2017). However, like in many developing nations, these fortunes have not manifested into meaningful development of the people's welfare condition. Rather, the delivery of processed crude oil products like petrol and gas in the country has declined due to corruption, smuggling, bureaucratic bottlenecks, mismanagement and inefficiencies (Ibanga, 2019).

Nigeria began to subsidize the petroleum industry around the 1980s after setting up its own petroleum company called the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). It was observed that an average Nigerian would be unable to afford one litre of petrol if not subsidized; this brought about the introduction of a subsidy policy to make fuel prices affordable for all. Despite this, petroleum price continues to increase with constant scarcity of fuel which was supposed to be stopped by the downstream sector deregulation. It was anticipated that the removal of the fuel subsidy policy would allow for competition in the sector resulting in the reduction of prices, and surplus commodities as well as efficiency and effectiveness (Cassy, 2018).

Interestingly, fuel subsidies have been a longstanding policy to reduce energy costs for consumers in Nigeria. However, these subsidies have also led to substantial fiscal challenges and economic inefficiencies. A study by the World Bank indicated that while reducing fuel subsidies could lead to an increase in Nigeria's gross domestic product, it might also have adverse effects on household incomes, particularly among poorer households (Sidig 2015). It is therefore not surprising, that Akwa Ibom State, one of Nigeria's major oil-producing states especially rural areas, face economic challenges. Research has shown that the removal of fuel subsidies negatively impact the living standards of rural populations in oil-producing communities. (Udoh *et al* 2024). Even Udoh and Mboho (2022) has posited that the well-being of rural dwellers in communities is a matter of international strategy. With fuel prices rising, the expenses associated with commuting to markets, schools, and healthcare facilities have increased. This escalation not only affects personal mobility but also households in rural communities as higher costs in transporting their goods, lead to reduced profit margins and economic strain. Furthermore, the agricultural sector, which is the backbone of rural economy, has also been significantly impacted. In households where they are farmers, their reliance on fuel to power machinery and transport produce has led to increased operational expenses, which are often passed on to consumers through higher food prices. This situation exacerbates the worsening state of food access and places additional financial burdens on households that are already vulnerable.

Therefore, how does the removal of fuel subsidy impact household food access in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area? To what extent does the removal of fuel subsidy also

impact income generation opportunities in the study area? Does fuel subsidy removal impact healthcare access by households? Providing answers to the questions raised above is the objective of the study. There is limited empirical research that specifically examines the impact of fuel subsidy removal on rural households, particularly in rural areas. Most studies tend to focus on urban areas or national-level impacts, leaving a gap in understanding how rural communities are uniquely affected by such policies. This research will bridge that gap by providing localized empirical data about the direct and indirect consequences of fuel subsidy removal on rural households. The paper is divided into five parts. Section one deals with the introduction. Section two reviews the literature and the theoretical framework of the research. The third section shows materials and methods. Section four presents the findings and discussion, and then section five provides the conclusion, policy recommendations, and future research directions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Fuel Subsidy

Subsidy exists when the government helps the consumers of a particular product to pay a price lower than the prevailing market price of that commodity (Kadiri & Lawal, 2016). Some authors like Agu et al., (2018) see it as a kind of market manipulation whereby the government fixes the price of the commodity below its actual market price and pays the difference to the retailers. In this case, the government fixes the pump price of fuel below the actual market price and the difference is paid to the importers and marketers by the government.

According to Onyeizugbe & Onwuka (2012), fuel subsidy means that a proportion of the amount consumers are to pay for the usage of petroleum products is paid by the government to relieve the burden of the price. The government of Nigeria removed the fuel subsidy declaring that the prices being paid by the citizens are lower than what they are supposed to pay when compared with those of the international market. Fuel subsidy could also be viewed according to Majekodunmi (2013) as a government program which is created to lessen the price to be paid by Nigerians for oil products. These oil products include Automated Gas Oil (Diesel), Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) and Dual Purpose Kerosene (DPK). Fuel subsidy removal policies are very responsive to the structure of an economy, a country's level of development, state of the economy and political system. Studies have shown that countries that have succeeded in fuel subsidy removal have taken a slow approach and done a lot of research before implementation. This can be made possible by the effective communication as well as a high level of trust between the government and its citizens (Centre for Public Policy Alternatives, 2012). Iyobhebhe (2012) argued that many Nigerians have access to affordable petroleum products through fuel subsidy. Petroleum subsidy represents universal benefit and not a benefit targeted specifically at the poor (Cornia & Stewart, 2015). Similarly, Hobhebhe (2012) was of the opinion that subsidy is an indirect way of redistributing wealth to the poor and if stopped, government must find a way of compensating Nigerians, explain how the resulting inflation will be managed and how the savings from the removal of subsidy will be utilized. In addition, Akinwale *et al* (2013) claimed that a large number of the citizens have gravely opposed the governments' removal of fuel subsidies because it is against the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) which are aimed at reducing the level of poverty in the country. Poverty itself as posited by Mboho and Udoh (2018), added that, as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon, it goes beyond the condition of lack of resources. It

extends to social and gender inequality in Nigeria is not a new phenomenon (Udoh and Ekanem, 2024). It is a general problem to human existence, healthy relationships and development.

Rural Communities

Rural Communities according to Egbe (2014) are areas that are lacking the most in terms of basic infrastructures for meaningful development. These infrastructures include good roads, clean water supply, health facilities, electricity, and quality education among others. The dwellers of rural areas according to him engage in subsistence farming and are also characterized by low standard of living, neglected socially and politically. Rural areas represent a very important sector of the Nigerian economy as they represent a home for Nigerian fortunes. This is evidenced by the fact that these communities produce virtually all the food products in the country, possess both human and raw materials for industrial processes, provide shelter in times of national crises, and preserve the cultural values in the society to mention but a few (Raji *et al*, 2017). These rural communities suffer meaningful development and are affected by many of the economic policies in the country. This is because they are less vocal, far away from the government and as such cannot make their voices heard. Yet, they still possess the majority population in a developing nation like Nigeria where over 70% of the country's population still live in rural areas. Thus there is a need to develop these areas to have meaningful development economically as well as in other sectors of the country (Nyagba, 2009). According to Udoh and Mboho (2022), the community will develop more when initiatives such as the use of local resources, labour and local organizational or managerial ability are done. Therefore, it can be said that communities without many intergroup rivalries will develop more. This is in line with the assertion by Effiong *et al* (2018), who posited that societies worldwide have had very disturbing phases in their history, as characterized by unending intergroup rivalries

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Dependency Theory argues that resources flow from periphery (underdeveloped) nations to core (developed) nations, and those economic policies that reinforce this flow of wealth can perpetuate poverty in the periphery. In the context of this research, this theory can help explain how the fuel subsidy removal disproportionately affects rural communities, deepening their economic dependency on external systems (e.g. the oil industry or urban economies) rather than encouraging local development. The assumption of the theory includes:

Economic dependence: Rural areas in developing countries, like Nigeria, are often dependent on external or centralized policies and systems. Fuel subsidies, when present, act as a form of government support to reduce the cost burden on rural communities. Their removal may leave these areas increasingly dependent on external markets for energy and goods.

Vulnerability to policy changes: Rural households are assumed to be highly vulnerable to economic policies, such as fuel subsidy removal because they have limited economic alternatives and are often excluded from the benefits of development or resource redistribution.

Fuel subsidy removal deepens the dependency of rural areas on external economic

forces, such as oil prices or government interventions. In places like Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, where access to alternative energy resources and economic activities is limited, the policy changes increase economic vulnerabilities. The study will explore how dependency on external factors (like oil subsidies and transportation costs) limits local economic resilience and hinders rural development.

METHODOLOGY

For this study on Fuel Subsidy removal and its impacts on rural households in Ikot Ekpene local government area, Akwa Ibom State, a quantitative research methodology was chosen. This approach was selected to provide empirical evidence on the specific impacts of fuel subsidy removal on rural households in the area. The research used a cross-sectional design to collect data at a specific point in time, offering a snapshot of how the policy has impacted rural communities. The target population for this study consists solely of rural households in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, which is known for its predominantly rural demographic. A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure that a representative sample was selected from the rural communities. The stratification process divided the local government area into different rural villages, with each village representing a distinct stratum. Random sampling was then applied to select households from each village to participate in the study. The goal is to ensure equal representation across the different rural communities within the area.

The sample size for this study included 400 household heads across the selected rural villages such as Ifuho, Ikot Offiong, Ikot Otto, Abiaokpo, Ikot Essien and Nkap ensure that the data gathered is statistically significant and will provide a clear understanding of the broader impact of the policy. Data collection will be conducted using structured questionnaires, which were administered to the selected household heads in person.

The questionnaires were administered in either English or Annang language, depending on the respondent's preference, ensuring that the participants fully understood and provided accurate responses. Data collected from the respondents were inputted into statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) software for Chi-square analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means will be used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

RESULTS

Out of 400 questionnaires administered to respondents, 382 questionnaires representing 95.5% were returned while 18 questionnaire representing 4.5% were not returned. The socio-demographic characteristics analysis of the study respondents shown that 165 respondents representing 43% were male respondents who returned the questionnaire while 217 respondents representing 57% were female respondents who returned the questionnaire. A total of 130 respondents representing 34% were between the ages of 21 to 25, 100 respondents representing 26% were between the ages of 26 to 40, 87 respondents representing 23% were between the ages of 41 to 50 while respondents representing 17% falls between the ages of 51 and above. For their marital status, 183 (48%) of the respondents were single, 96 (25%) were married, 58 (15%) were widowed, and 45 (12%) were divorced. On level of education of respondents, analysis shown that the study respondents with WAEC/SSCE were 78 (20%), Diploma 72 (19%), B.S.c. 83 (22%),

MBA/M.Sc. 82 (21%), PhD and above 67 (18%). For religious affiliation, 379 respondents representing 99.2% were Christians, while 3 respondents representing 0.8% were Muslims.

**Table 1: Fuel subsidy removal and Household food access in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area
Chi-Square Distribution Table**

Cell	Fo	Fe	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{Fe}$
A	75	86.51	- 11.51	132.48	1.53
B	72	64.08	7.92	62.73	0.98
C	45	34.71	10.29	105.88	3.05
D	20	18.69	1.31	1.72	0.09
E	87	75.49	11.51	132.48	1.75
F	48	55.92	- 7.92	62.73	1.12
G	20	30.29	- 10.29	105.88	3.49
H	15	16.31	-1.31	1.72	0.11
					$\sum x^2 = 12.12$

Degree of freedom = (R-1)(C-1)
 = (2-1)(4-1)
 = 1x3
 = 3

The level of significance = 0.05
 Calculated value = 47.09
 Critical table value = 7.8

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 47.09 is greater than the critical table value of 7.8 the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Conclusion: From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and household food access in Ikot Ekpene. Local Government Area.

**Table 2: Fuel subsidy removal and Income generation by households in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area
Chi-Square Distribution Table**

Cell	Fo	Fe	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{Fe}$
A	80	62.96	17.04	290.36	4.61
B	50	44.55	5.45	29.70	0.66
C	66	62.96	3.04	9.24	0.15
D	18	14.53	3.47	12.04	0.83
E	50	67.04	- 17.04	290.36	4.33
F	42	47.45	- 5.45	29.70	0.63
G	65	67.04	- 2.04	4.16	0.06
H	12	15.47	- 3.47	12.04	0.78
					$\sum x^2 = 12.05$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (R-1)(C-1) \\ &= (2-1)(4-1) \\ &= 1 \times 3 \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The level of significance} &= 0.05 \\ \text{Calculated value} &= 12.12 \\ \text{Critical table value} &= 7.8 \end{aligned}$$

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 12.12 is greater than the critical table value of 7.8, the null hypothesis H_0 will be rejected.

Conclusion: From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and income generation by households in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Table 3: Fuel subsidy removal and healthcare access of households in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area
Chi-Square Distribution Table

Cell	Fo	Fe	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{Fe}$
A	80	62.96	17.04	290.36	4.61
B	50	44.55	5.45	29.70	0.66
C	66	62.96	3.04	9.24	0.15
D	18	14.53	3.47	12.04	0.83
E	50	67.04	- 17.04	290.36	4.33
F	42	47.45	- 5.45	29.70	0.63
G	65	67.04	- 2.04	4.16	0.06
H	12	15.47	- 3.47	12.04	0.78
					$\sum x^2 = 12.05$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (R-1)(C-1) \\ &= (2-1)(4-1) \\ &= 1 \times 3 \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The level of significance} &= 0.05 \\ \text{Calculated value} &= 12.05 \\ \text{Critical table value} &= 7.8 \end{aligned}$$

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 12.05 is greater than the critical table value of 7.8, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Conclusion: From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and access to health care by households in Ikot Ekpene L.G.A

DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The study revealed that the household food access in the understudied communities have changed since the removal of the fuel subsidy, thus depicting that there is a significant

relationship between fuel subsidy removal and people standard of living in the State. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 45% strongly agreed that there are changes in household food access in the respondent(s) community since the removal of fuel subsidy

The study found out that income generation by households has been affected since the removal of the fuel subsidy, thus depicting that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and access to education, healthcare and transportation by households. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 32% agreed that there have been the ability of household to generate income as before, since the removal of fuel subsidy.

The study revealed that households have revealed having difficulty in healthcare access as a result of the removal of the fuel subsidy. The findings depicted that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and changes in Food Security and Nutritional status of households of the study area. From the questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 42.4% agreed that households in Ikot Ekpene LGA has undergone dietary changes or sacrifices due to changes in food prices after the removal of fuel subsidy.

CONCLUSION

The removal of the fuel subsidy in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area has led to significant adverse effects on the living conditions of households. First, fuel subsidy removal has strained access to affordable food, with many households experiencing reduced access to essential commodities. As transportation costs rose, so did the prices of goods, especially agricultural products, thereby affecting food security in these rural communities. Second, income generation has also been severely impacted, as rising costs and decreased productivity have left many households struggling to maintain their previous income levels. The agricultural sector, which is the backbone of the rural economy, has seen operational costs surge, contributing to a decline in overall household income. Finally, healthcare access has become more challenging, with increased transportation costs and reduced disposable income making it harder for rural households to seek medical attention, especially when healthcare facilities are located far from their homes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the significant challenges brought about by the fuel subsidy removal, several recommendations can be made to mitigate the impact on rural households in Ikot Ekpene and similar communities:

1. Targeted Compensation Programs: The government should introduce targeted compensation mechanisms that directly benefit vulnerable households. This could include subsidies for food, healthcare, and transportation to help alleviate the increased costs faced by rural households.
2. Alternative Energy Solutions: Promoting the use of alternative and renewable energy sources, such as solar energy, could reduce reliance on costly fuel. Providing incentives or subsidies for rural communities to invest in clean energy could help reduce fuel dependence and improve household resilience.
3. Support for the Agricultural Sector: Given the critical role of agriculture in rural economies, the government should consider providing direct support to farmers in

the form of subsidies for fuel and agricultural inputs. This would help mitigate the impact of rising operational costs and ensure food security.

4. Improvement of Healthcare Infrastructure: Strengthening healthcare access by building more healthcare facilities in rural areas and providing affordable transportation options for rural dwellers can improve healthcare access and reduce the burden on households seeking medical care.

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